

REAL-TIME DAMAGE VISUALIZATION OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES SUBJECTED TO LOW-SPEED IMPACT

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ABSTRACT We present a systematic experimental investigation of the generation and subsequent evolution of dynamic failure modes in model composite laminates and sandwich structures subjected to low-speed impact. High-speed photography and dynamic photoelasticity were utilized to study the nature and sequence of such failure modes. In all cases, delamination appeared first. The shear-dominated delamination crack kinked into the core layer, then, propagated as the opening-dominated matrix crack in the adjacent weak layer.

KEYWORDS: Low-speed Impact, Impact damage, matrix cracking, delamination, sandwich structures

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials and sandwich structures have diverse and technologically interesting applications in many areas of engineering [1-3]. While their static failure characteristics have been investigated extensively in the past years, their dynamic counterparts have remained elusive [1-5]. There are two major categories of failure observed in post-mortem studies based on the material constitutions of layered structures. The first major failure category is inter-layer failure between bonded layers at an interface. This is often referred to as delamination in composite laminates or interfacial debonding in thin films or sandwich structures. Generally, two distinct inter-layer failure modes are observed. The first one involves opening-dominated inter-layer cracking or “delamination buckling” [6-7]. The second one involves shear-dominated inter-layer cracks or “shear delaminations”, and often occurs in layered materials subjected to out-of-plane impact [8-10]. The second major category is referred to as intra-layer failure. There are three possible intra-layer failure modes depending on the material constitution. The first one is called intra-layer cracking or matrix cracking. This type of cracking often occurs inside the matrix of fiber-reinforced composites or within the soft core of sandwich structures [11]. Another possible intra-layer failure is the failure of reinforcements such as fiber breakage and fiber kinking within a layer [12]. The fifth possible intra-layer failure mode is interfacial debonding between the matrix material and the reinforcement such as debonding between the particle/fiber and matrix occurring within a constituent layer. For most layered materials, the presence of such highly complicated dynamic failure modes and the inaccessibility of internal damage to direct observation, explain the fact that only the final impact damage characteristics of such structures are usually discussed in the open literature. Indeed, the sequence, nature and interaction of such failure process were never properly clarified. Notable exception to this rule is the early studies of Takeda et al. [13], who observed the evolution and sequence of matrix cracking and delamination failure in glass fiber composite laminates under ballistic impact. However, the equivalent situation involving low or intermediate-speed impact loading has yet to be investigated. In perhaps the first attempt to visualize impact failure in a sandwich structure used in Naval applications, Samenski and Rosakis tested thin sections of such structures composed of PVC foam cores, sandwiched between E-glass faceplates [14]. A

pulsed laser was used to illuminate the specimens from the back side and a high-speed camera recorded the deformation and failure events. Only opening-dominated matrix cracks in the core layer were observed. The inability of back-lit photography to visualize the failure process completely, motivates the use of partially transparent model sandwich systems which allow the use of full field optical techniques capable of capturing the nucleation and growth of cracks and their transition from one mode to the other. The objectives of the current work are to conduct systematic experimental studies of the time evolution and nature of different impact failure modes and to investigate their interactions. Through these model experiments, we try to identify the basic physical phenomena, and to provide guidance for theoretical models and much needed validation of numerical codes.

For many complex engineering problems, model experiments may prove extremely useful as intermediate steps, which reveal the basic physics of the problem and provide relatively straightforward explanations of the failure patterns observed in post-mortem observations. A striking example of this approach was provided by Riley and Dally [15], who designed a model metal/polymer layered system subjected to dynamic loading. Their model configuration was designed to simulate stress waves in layered structures. A similarly successful approach was adopted by Walter and Ravichandran [16], who designed a model aluminum/PMMA/aluminum specimen to simulate and visualize the static debonding and matrix cracking process in ceramic matrix composites. In order to simulate the difficult three-dimensional problem of the out-of-plane impact of real composite and sandwich structures and to simultaneously preserve the essence of the failure phenomena involved, we introduce a two-dimensional, plane stress specimen, which represents a cross-sectional cut of the layered material as illustrated in Figure 1. For this type of model specimen, the failure process is easy to record, visualize and analyze. In designing these model two-dimensional sandwich specimens, it is important to select model materials whose elastic mismatch is similar to that of materials used in real engineering applications. Selecting similar Dundurs' parameters [1] may ensure similarity of the elasto-static response for the interfacial mechanics problem. Meanwhile, selecting model material combinations with similar ratios of wave speeds of two constitution materials to the real structure is perhaps the most important consideration in the dynamic case. Also, the ratio of inter-layer and intra-layer strengths (or toughnesses) is important. These three issues provide similarity rules to connect real structures to our models tests.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A 4340-carbon steel was employed to simulate the stiff and strong fiberglass faceplates of sandwich structures or 0° plies of cross-ply laminates. The polymeric material, which was used to simulate the weak layer, such as sandwich cores or 90° plies in cross-ply laminates, is Homalite-100. Some physical properties of these model materials were reported in [4]. The adhesive used to bond the metal/polymer interface is Weldon-10. The detailed properties of this adhesive and the effect of interfacial strength variation on dynamic failure mode selection were reported in [17]. Two different types of model specimen geometries were designed and tested. Type A specimens have equal layer widths (38.1 mm). They contain two metal layers with one polymer layer sandwiched between them with the same length 254 mm. Type B specimens involve two thin metal layers and one polymer layer (width 38.1 mm). This type of specimens is quite similar in geometry (ratio of core to faceplate thickness) to realistic sandwich structures. The length of type B specimens is 508 mm because the purpose of type B specimens is to explore the impact failure patterns with least edge effects. All two types of specimens have the same out-of-plane thickness of 6.35mm.

The majority of experiments were performed using dynamic photoelasticity. A laser beam was transmitted through the specimen and the resulting fringe pattern was recorded by a high-speed camera. A

Cordin 330A rotating-mirror type high-speed film camera was used to record the images. During the impact test, a projectile was fired by the gas gun and impacted the specimen center. The generation of isochromatic fringe patterns is governed by the stress-optic law. The fringe patterns observed are proportional to contours of constant maximum in-plane shear stress, $\hat{\tau}_{\max} = (\hat{\sigma}_1 - \hat{\sigma}_2)/2$. More experimental details can be found in [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Failure Process in Short Specimens with Equal Layer Widths (Type A)

Because the diameter of a laser beam (100 μm) is less than the minimum specimen length (254 mm), in order to observe all possible dynamic failure modes present in each case, the field of view had to be moved from one location to another for each specimen configuration under the same impact and material conditions. Figure 2 presents a series of photoelastic images of the Homalite layer of a type A specimen. In all these experiments, the projectile impacted the center of the bottom metal layer. The dark circular spot at the upper right corner is a scaling mark (diameter 6.35 mm) bonded on the specimen. The thin horizontal dark line, seen around the center of every image, is the streak line of the camera. At first, the field of view was centered on the middle of the specimen because it was close to the impact position and failure was expected to initiate from this zone. As shown in Figure 2 (b), about 158 μs after impact, two inter-layer cracks at the lower interface entered the field of view and propagated towards the specimen center. Before that time, there was no visible damage within the field of view. Later on (around 182 μs), the two inter-layer cracks, identified by the moving concentration of fringes at their tips, are seen to meet each other in Figure 2 (d). Similar to shear-dominated interfacial cracks in bimetals [18], those inter-layer cracks are also shear-dominated. Because the Homalite and steel layers are still in contact up to that time, no visual evidence of decohesion is apparent in the images, although these cracks have already broken the interface in a combination of compression and shear.

In order to conclusively identify the origins of the upper and lower inter-layer cracks, the field of view was once more moved to the specimen edge as shown in Figure 3 (a). After impact at the specimen center, the stress waves in the bottom steel layer propagated towards the edge creating a visible head wave structure on the lower wave speed polymer side (see Figure 3 (b)). Right after the stress wave reached the free edge, due to the existence of a stress singularity at the bi-material corner [19], an inter-layer crack initiated at the lower interface as seen in Figure 3 (c). This crack propagated towards the specimen center. After around 160 μs , another inter-layer crack initiated at the upper interface also moving towards the center. This upper inter-layer crack soon kinked into the core layer and branched into a fan of multiple intra-layer cracks. Here the cracks kinking to the central Homalite layer are opening-dominated rather than shear-dominated, although they are often referred to “shear matrix cracks” or “shear core” in the literature [3,5,20-21]. Because fiber-reinforced composite materials show transversely isotropic mechanical properties [22], mode I opening cracks rather than mode II shear cracks occur in the 90° central layer based on fracture mechanics theories.

Based on experimental observations from different fields of view, the major dynamic failure modes and sequence in model specimens can be summarized in Figure 4. After the stress wave reaches the free edges, two shear-dominated inter-layer cracks initiate and propagate towards the specimen center. These shear cracks separate the whole lower interface and a Rayleigh surface wave forms on the separated free surface. At a later stage, inter-layer cracks also originate from the upper interface at the free edge and travel towards the specimen center. However, these upper inter-layer cracks soon kink into the core layer or weak 90° layer to form opening-dominated intra-layer cracks. Under certain circumstances (e. g., if the

core material is very brittle), such kinked cracks may also branch into a fan of multiple branches fragmenting the core layer. The model experiments seem to capture the basic nature of the post-mortem impact failure modes observed in real sandwich structures [14]. Indeed, the kinked matrix cracks of the core layer of the glass fiber/foam core sandwich shown in Figure 4 (e) seems to follow the same initiation and propagation process as the kinked intra-layer crack in the model three-layer specimens schematically shown in Figure 4 (d).

Failure Process in Long Sandwich-style Specimens (Type B)

To reduce the free edge effects, we tested long sandwich-style specimens of type B (see Figure 5). As shown in Figure 5 (d), at 79 μs after impact, an inter-layer crack tip is seen at the lower interface. This crack is similar to our previously observed inter-layer fractures but has not originated at the specimen free edge, which for type B specimens is far away from our field of view. Indeed, if this crack originated from the specimen free edge, it would take at least 150 μs to enter the field of view. Closer scrutiny reveals that this crack originates from a much closer location to the impact point. This location is marked by the circle in Figure 5 (c). The crack nucleates at a location where the inter-layer shear stress reaches a local maximum, whose value equals the shear strength of the bond. The shear stress component σ_{12} at the specimen centerline will always vanish because of this symmetry but is expected to anti-symmetrically increase away from the centerline as compressive waves begin to spread along the steel faceplate. The hypothesis presented above is consistent with the finite element analyses [5,9,23], where two clear peak values of the interlaminar shear stress were shown to symmetrically move away from the impact site. As a result of these observations, the scenario that seems to be emerging is as follows: shear-dominated cracks are generated at two points to the right and left of the center line and move backwards towards the impact point. A series of photographs confirming the existence of an inter-layer crack coming from the right hand side of the impact point is shown in Figure 5. Indeed Figure 5 (c) corresponds to nucleation of this crack while Figures 5 (d) (e) and (f) confirm its high-speed motion towards the impact site. As this inter-layer crack and its symmetric companion from the left, meet above the impact point they create a central shear delamination between the core and the bottom faceplate. The crack speed is very high as evident from the shear shock wave that appears as a dark inclined line radiating from its moving tip (Figures 5 (e) and (f)). Figure 6 corresponds to another impact experiment which featured the same load and material conditions shown in Figure 5. The end point of the central delamination described above is denoted by A. Point A in Figure 6 is corresponding to the old location of the maximum inter-layer shear stress. This point can now act as a stress concentration from which further damage (to the core as well as to the rest of the interface) will subsequently evolve. Indeed as seen in Figure 6, intra-layer cracks now are generated and propagated into the core (along AC), also accompanied by a new inter-layer debond (along AB) also originating at point A.

Figure 7 summarizes the proposed failure evolution sequence for the long sandwich style specimens described above. One point that should be made clear here is that following the formation of the central (shear) delamination, the choice of the inclination angle β and the possibility of further delamination along the bottom interface depend on the impact speed and on the relative values of the matrix material and interfacial bond strengths (toughnesses). The same is true for the exact locations of points A and B. However, we expect that if impact speeds are high enough to promote this localized failure mode, the general features described here will continue appearing even as the projectile speed increases further. An extension of the present work concentrating on the effect of bond strengths and impact speeds on dynamic failure is presented in [17]. For the initiation of intra-layer cracks (matrix cracks), previous researchers theorized that such cracks initiated from the center of the weak layer and propagated toward adjacent interfaces to lead to inter-layer cracks or delaminations. However, no real-time experimental evidence was ever observed to support such a scenario. Here, we already show that the intra-layer cracks always

initiate at the interface immediately following the formation of the shear-dominated delamination in a form of crack kinking.

CONCLUSIONS

In all cases described in this paper, delamination is the dominant dynamic failure mode for composite and sandwich structures subjected to low-speed impact. In terms of fracture nature, it is shear-dominated. Matrix cracking often initiates at the interface as a result of inter-layer delamination kinking into the adjacent layer. It is a typical opening-dominated crack. If free edge effects at the bimaterial corners are eliminated, delamination initiates from positions where the inter-layer shear stress reaches a local maximum. Intra-layer (matrix) cracks also kink from these positions into the adjacent layer.

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REFERENCES

1. Hutchinson, J. W. and Suo, Z., *Advances in Applied Mechanics*, (1998); 29:63-191.
2. Rajapakse, Y. D. S., *Sandwich Construction 3*, Vol. II, (1998), pp. 475-486.
3. Abrate, S., *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, (1994);47:517-544.
4. L. R. Xu and A. J. Rosakis *International J. of Solids and Structures*, 39:4215-35 (2002)
5. Sun, C. T. and Rechak, S. *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Eighth Conference)*. ASTM STP 972, J.D. Whitcomb, Ed., ASTM, Philadelphia, (1988). pp. 97-123.
6. Vizzini, A.J. and Lagace, P.A., *Journal of Composite Materials*, (1987);21:1106-1117.
7. Kadomateas, G. A. AMD-Vol. 235, *Thick Composites for Load Bearing Structures*, (Y.D.S. Rajapakse and G.A. Kadomateas, Ed.) (1999). pp. 51-60.
8. Wu, H. T. and Springer, G. S., *J. of Composite Materials*, (1988);22:518-532.
9. Choi, H. Y., Wu, H. T. and Chang, F.-K. , *J. Composite Materials*, (1991);25:1012-1038.
10. Lambros J. and Rosakis A. J., *Experimental Mechanics*, (1997);37:360-366.
11. Lee, J.-W. and Daniel, I. M. *J. Composite Materials*, (1990);24:1225-1243.
12. H.T. Hahn and Williams, J.G., *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (7th Conf.)*, ASTM STP 893 J.M. Whitney, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1986, pp. 115-139.
13. Takeda, N., Sierakowski, R. L., Ross, C. A. and Malvern, L. E., *Experimental Mechanics*, (1982);22:19 65.
14. Semenski, D. and Rosakis, A. J., *Proceedings of the 17th Danubia-Adria Symposium on Experimental Mechanics in Solid Mechanics*, Prague, (1999).
15. Riley, W. F. & Dally, J. W., *Geophysics*, (1966);31:881-99.
16. Walter, M.E. and Ravichandran, G., *Experimental Mechanics*, (1997);37:130—135.
17. Xu, L. R. and A. J. Rosakis, *International J. of Solids and Structures*, 39: 4237-48 (2002).
18. Rosakis, A. J., Samudrala, O., Singh, R. P. and Shukla, A., *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, (1998);46:1789-1813.
19. Williams, M., L., *J. Applied Mechanics*, (1952);19:526-528.
20. Wen, H. M., Reddy, T. Y., Reid, S. R. and Soden, P. D., *Key Engineering Materials*, (1998);141-143:501-552.
21. Karbhari, V. M. and Rydin, R. W., *J. of Material Science*, (1999);34:5641-5648.
22. Vinson, J. R. and Sierakowski, R. L., *The Behavior of Structures Composed of Composite Materials*. Martinus, Nijhoff Publishers, Dordrecht, (1986).
23. Yu, C. and Ortiz, M., Private communications. (2001)

Figure 1 Model layered specimens are idealized cross sections of real structures subjected to out-of-plane impact

Figure 2 The failure process of a three-layer specimen with equal layer widths. The central field of view reveals the early occurrence of shear-dominated delamination at the lower interface.

Figure 3 An edge view of impact damage evolution. Inter-layer delaminations are shown to form at the intersection of, first lower, and then upper interfaces with the specimen edge. A fan of kinked intra-layer cracks branches into the core layer from the upper interface.

Figure 4 Conceptual summary of typical failure modes and sequence in a short three-layer specimen with equal layer widths. Figure (e) is a comparison with a post-impact picture of a real sandwich specimen

Figure 5. Nucleation of an intersonic inter-layer crack at the vicinity of the impact point. The specimen (type B) is long enough to eliminate the edge interference.

Figure 6. Local view of the post-mortem damage in a long sandwich-style specimen

Figure 7. Failure sequence observed in long sandwich-style specimens with minimal edge effects.